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IMPACT OF HIGH-INTENSITY INTERVAL TRAINING (HIIT) ON HEART RATE VARIABILITY IN RUNNERS

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Abstract: Introduction: Heart rate variability (HRV) measures have been increasingly used to assess autonomic regulation changes induced by training. HRV analysis is a valuable tool for monitoring training load responses, physical conditioning, and overtraining in athletes. Objective: To analyze heart rate variability and performance in runners undergoing a high-intensity interval training (HIIT) protocol. Methods: Eleven well-trained runners (age: 31 ± 5.78 years; running experience: 10.23 ± 6.11 years; best 5K time: 16.94 ± 1.82 minutes) participated in the study. A maximal incremental treadmill test was conducted pre- and post-training to determine maximal aerobic speed (MAS). The test began at 10 km/h, increasing by 1 km/h every 2 minutes without rest. The HIIT program lasted four weeks, with two sessions per week. Training intensity was progressively adjusted. Each session included 1-minute intervals at a percentage of MAS, alternated with 1-minute active recovery at 50% of the corresponding load, until exhaustion or a 90-minute ceiling. R-R intervals were recorded at rest using a POLAR® RS800cx monitor at four time points: before the initial test (PRE HIIT), before the first session in week 3 (110% MAS), before the first session in week 4 (Taper), and before the final test (POST HIIT). HRV was analyzed using Kubios software in time domain, nonlinear parameters, and overall HRV metrics. Statistical analyses included Student's t-test (VO₂ max and MAS) and One-Way ANOVA with Tukey and Dunn post hoc tests (resting HRV). Results: Positive adaptations were observed with maintained cardiorespiratory fitness and resting HRV. Autonomic modulation adapted to training load, with HRV reduction during intense phases (110% MAS and Taper) and recovery post-training. Significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found in SDNN, RMSSD, and SD2 between phases. Conclusion: HRV is sensitive to HIIT effects, proving effective for monitoring

cardiac autonomic regulation and guiding training load. HIIT also supports performance maintenance in runners.

Keywords: HRV, HIIT, Autonomic Regulation, Heart Rate, Street race.

I. INTRODUCTION

Road running is a sport that has been growing significantly in Brazil, with concern for health being one of its main attractions, followed by the low cost of participation [1]. Sports training programs play a crucial role in supporting runners and promoting this activity across the country [2].

Both professional and amateur athletes engaged in competitive levels strive persistently to improve their performance without compromising their health. The primary goal is to maximize positive adaptations while minimizing negative outcomes such as decreased performance, overtraining, or injury. Targeted training under the supervision of qualified professionals is recognized as essential for progress in this sport. One of the major challenges faced by amateur athletes is balancing training with their daily routines. In this context, high-intensity interval training (HIIT) appears to be a practical alternative, capable of inducing rapid adaptations and improving physical fitness within a short period [3].

According to the 2020 guidelines from the World Health Organization (WHO), regular physical activity provides essential health benefits, including improved

cardiorespiratory fitness and reduced cardiovascular risk. However, some studies have shown that excessive and uncontrolled exercise may be harmful, potentially increasing the risk of cardiac morbidity and mortality [4]. Despite concerns among some fitness professionals regarding the potential for injury, HIIT remains among the top five global fitness trends, as reported by the annual survey of the American College of Sports Medicine (ACSM) [5].

The importance of monitoring physical conditioning to allow individualized training adjustments and enhance athletic performance is well established. In this regard, resting heart rate and heart rate variability (HRV) have been increasingly used as monitoring tools [6].

Heart rate variability (HRV) enables the assessment of autonomic regulation of cardiac rhythm and reflects the body's responsiveness to physiological and environmental stimuli. It also serves as an indicator of the body's capacity to adapt to exercise stimuli [7]. HRV can thus be used to monitor training adaptations and fatigue in athletes [8] and is also recognized as a marker of cardiovascular health status [9].

Autonomic regulation of heart rate (HR) provides insight into training adaptation. Appropriate training loads increase parasympathetic activity, indicating positive adaptations, while prolonged overload leads to increased sympathetic modulation and decreased parasympathetic activity—signs of negative adaptation [10]. Inadequate recovery from training can also reduce HRV indices, signaling accumulated fatigue and exhaustion. Consequently, HRV serves as a physiological response marker that helps determine an athlete's readiness for subsequent training sessions [6].

Continuous monitoring of athletes' HRV is essential to identifying health-related variables influenced by autonomic regulation and training load. This monitoring supports the selection of appropriate training methods and adjustment of workloads [11,12]. Short-duration HRV measurements have been shown to be a practical and feasible approach to integrate into daily training routines [13].

Considering that HIIT is an accessible and comprehensive physical training option for runners, and that HRV is a clinical tool with predictive value for both health and athletic performance, understanding how HIIT affects HRV is of great relevance. In this context, investigating the physiological adaptations of HRV in runners undergoing HIIT may assist health professionals and coaches in prescribing this type of training appropriately, thereby supporting the maintenance or enhancement of athletic performance.

Despite the growing body of research on HIIT and its implications for performance [14,15], and the use of HRV in various scientific domains [7,16], it remains unclear whether HRV is a sensitive tool for monitoring this specific training

model. Therefore, the aim of this study was to analyze the effects of a HIIT protocol on HRV indices and running performance.

Based on the literature and the objectives of this research, the following hypotheses were established: the high-intensity interval training (HIIT) protocol will promote significant changes in heart rate variability (HRV) indices of amateur runners; it will also improve their running performance. Furthermore, it is hypothesized that positive performance adaptations will be associated with increased parasympathetic activity, as reflected in higher HRV indices. Conversely, the null hypothesis is that HIIT will not induce significant modifications either in HRV indices or in running performance.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was designed as a longitudinal and prospective clinical trial [17], conducted at a specialized running training center (C.T. Danilo Faria) in Uberlândia, Brazil. All training sessions occurred at the same time of day and under professional supervision. The study received ethical approval from the Human Research Ethics Committee of the Federal University of Uberlândia (approval number: 3.397.582, CAAE: 13624419.2.0000.5152). All participants signed an informed consent form in accordance with Resolution CNS 466/12.

Participants

The sample consisted of 11 trained male runners, with a mean age of 31 ± 5.78 years, an average of 10.23 ± 6.11 years of running experience, and a 5-km personal best time of 16.94 ± 1.82 minutes. Eligibility criteria excluded individuals who had used medications or supplements in the 30 days prior to or during the intervention, as well as those with musculoskeletal injuries, cardiovascular diseases, or thyroid disorders. All participants were informed about the procedures, benefits, and potential risks of the study.

Incremental Treadmill Test:

Participants underwent an incremental treadmill test (Movement E.740). Following a warm-up, the test began at 10 km/h with 1 km/h increases every 2 minutes, without rest between stages. The treadmill incline was maintained at 1% throughout [18]. Participants were verbally encouraged to maintain effort until exhaustion [19]. A safety harness system was used to prevent falls and preserve performance.

Maximal running speed (V_{max}) was calculated using the equation for incomplete stages proposed by Kuipers [20]: $V_{max} = V_{complete} + (t/T \times V_{increment})$, where t is the time (in seconds) sustained in the incomplete stage, T is 120 seconds, and $V_{increment}$ is 1 km/h. Maximal oxygen uptake (VO_{2max}) was estimated using the ACSM's formula [21]: $VO_{2max} = (0.2 \times speed) + (0.9 \times speed \times$

incline) + 3.5, with speed = V_{max} and incline = 1%. The speed reached at exhaustion was considered the Maximal Aerobic Speed (MAS).

Training Protocol:

The intervention lasted four weeks, with two training sessions per week, totaling eight sessions. Each session consisted of 1-minute high-intensity intervals at a given %MAS, followed by 1 minute of active recovery at 50% of that intensity. Sessions continued until voluntary exhaustion or a maximum of 90 minutes.

In week one, intensity was set at 90% MAS; in week two, 100% MAS; and in week three, 110% MAS. Week four (taper) included two recovery sessions at 110% MAS, but with only 50% of the average number of intervals performed in the third week.

Heart Rate Variability (HRV) Analysis at Rest:

Resting heart rate was recorded using a POLAR® RS800cx monitor with a 1000 Hz sampling rate. Participants remained in a supine position with spontaneous breathing for five minutes, following Task Force guidelines [22]. A 1-minute ultra-short-term HRV segment was extracted after signal stabilization [23,24]. RR interval data were transferred to Polar Pro Trainer 5® software. Visual inspection and moderate digital filtering were used to remove artifacts and ectopic beats. Data sets with >2% invalid RR intervals were excluded. The most stable segment was saved in ".txt" format, imported into Excel, and manually filtered [25]. HRV parameters were analyzed using Kubios® HRV 3.4.3 software [26], including: Time domain: average heart rate measured at rest (Mean RR), average of RR intervals (Mean HR), standard deviation of all RR intervals (SDNN), root mean square difference between successive RR intervals (RMSSD), percentage of adjacent RR intervals with a duration difference greater than 50 ms (pNN50), and Stress Index (SI); Nonlinear domain: short-term variability (SD1), long-term variability (SD2), and the ratio of SD2 to SD1 (SD2/SD1);

Autonomic indices: Parasympathetic (PNS) and Sympathetic (SNS) activity [27]. Data were collected at four time points: before the initial incremental test (PRE-HIIT), before the first session of week 3 (110% MAS), before the first taper session (week 4), and before the final incremental test (POST-HIIT).

Statistical Analysis:

Descriptive statistics (mean ± standard deviation) were used to characterize the sample. Data normality was verified using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Paired *t*-tests assessed differences in VO_{2max} and MAS between pre- and post-intervention. Repeated-measures one-way ANOVA evaluated changes in resting HRV over time, followed by Tukey's post hoc tests when appropriate. Non-parametric indices (RMSSD, SD1) were analyzed using Friedman's test

and Dunn's multiple comparison post hoc test. The significance level was set at $p < 0.05$ (two-tailed). All analyses were performed using GraphPad Prism 7 (GraphPad Prism Inc., San Diego, CA, USA).

III. RESULTS

The results of this study are presented as mean and standard deviation, with statistical significance established at a two-tailed p -value < 0.05 . The sample comprised 11 eligible recreational runners with a mean age of 31.09 ± 5.78 years and training history of 10.23 ± 6.11 years. Average performance in the 5-km distance was 16.94 ± 1.82 minutes in official races and 17.77 ± 2.52 minutes during training sessions. Anthropometric assessments showed a mean body weight of 65.23 ± 9.26 kg, height of 1.755 ± 0.06 m, and body mass index (BMI) of 21.11 ± 2.22 kg/m², consistent with a healthy range. Regarding cardiorespiratory fitness, VO_{2max} averaged 65.1 ± 6.2 mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹ pre-HIIT and 65.7 ± 5.4 mL·kg⁻¹·min⁻¹ post-HIIT, while maximal aerobic speed (MAS) increased from 18.49 ± 1.84 km/h to 18.67 ± 1.62 km/h. No statistically significant differences were found between pre- and post-training for either variable (VO_{2max} : $p = 0.6828$; MAS: $p = 0.6824$).

Table 1: Values referring to the means and standard deviation for the resting HRV variables.

	PRE HIIT	110% VAM	Taper	POS HIIT
	M ± DP	M ± DP	M ± DP	M ± DP
RR	1023±171,2	1037±130,7	1039±135,8	1058±160,3
HR	60,27±9,686	58,55±6,89	58,45±6,669	57,91±8,227
SDNN	57,34±36,72	34,93±15,87*	34,29±12,83*	47,32±17,26
RMSSD	58,58±42,47	34,58±18,89	36,04±13,43*	49,67±19,35
pNN50	22,22±22,05	14,36±17,27	16,94±12,28	29,48±17,19
SD1	41,82±30,35	24,72±13,49	25,71±9,585	35,44±13,84
SD2	68,11±43,97	41,77±19,17	40,05±18,15*	56,04±21,38
SD2/SD1	1,795±0,5046	1,776±0,5603	1,642±0,651	1,622±0,373
SI	11,36±6,929	14,13±5,863	14,06±3,836	10,34±2,901
PNS	0,9345±1,69	0,3609±0,926	0,4455±0,8501	0,8791±0,8911
SNS	0,0036±1,671	0,2418±1,111	0,1845±0,846	0,4209±0,6893

Data are presented as mean ± standard deviation. One-way ANOVA for repeated measures. * Significant p -value (two-tailed) < 0.050 : (SDNN: $p=0,0225$; RMSSD: $p=0,0430$; DP1: $p=0,0435$; DP2: $p=0,0304$). Tukey's test and Dunn's test for multiple comparisons. RR(ms): mean of RR intervals; HR(bpm): mean of beats per minute; SDNN(ms): Standard deviation of all RR intervals; RMSSD(ms): Root mean square differences between successive RR intervals. Number of pairs of RR intervals; pNN50(%): percentage of adjacent RR intervals with a difference in duration greater than 50ms; SD1(ms): short-term beat-to-beat RR variability from the Poincaré plot; SD2(ms): long-term beat-to-beat variability from the Poincaré plot; SD2/SD1: Ratio of SD2 to SD1; SI: Stress Index, square root of the Baevsky Stress Index; PNS Index: Parasympathetic nervous system activity compared to normal resting values; SNS Index: Sympathetic nervous system activity compared to normal resting values; ms: milliseconds; bpm: beats per minute.

An inverse relationship was observed between the progressive increase in HIIT intensity and the number of stimuli performed to exhaustion: 34.96 stimuli at 90% MAS (week 1), 22.46 at 100% (week 2), and 10.5 at 110% (week 3), with significant reductions ($p = 0.01$). During week 4 (taper), intensity remained at 110%, but stimulus volume was reduced to 50% of the previous week's average (5.25 stimuli). Finally, analysis of resting heart rate variability (HRV) revealed statistically significant changes in SDNN ($p = 0.0225$), RMSSD ($p = 0.0430$), and SD2 ($p = 0.0304$), while no significant differences were found for the remaining parameters.

IV. DISCUSSION

The present study aimed to examine the effects of a high-intensity interval training (HIIT) protocol on heart rate variability (HRV) indices and performance in endurance runners. The key findings reveal favorable physiological adaptations to the intervention, with preserved cardiorespiratory fitness and resting HRV. No statistically significant differences were observed in $\text{VO}_{2\text{max}}$ and maximal aerobic speed (MAS) between pre- and post-HIIT, suggesting that aerobic capacity was maintained throughout the intervention. However, fluctuations in autonomic cardiac modulation were identified, with reductions in HRV indices during periods of greater training load (110% MAS and taper), followed by post-intervention increases, returning to near-baseline levels. Statistically significant differences ($p < 0.05$) were found in SDNN (pre-HIIT vs. 110% MAS and taper), RMSSD (taper vs. post-HIIT), and SD2 (taper vs. pre-HIIT) (Table 1).

The $\text{VO}_{2\text{max}}$ and MAS values remained stable, which is notable considering the high initial aerobic conditioning of participants. The average MAS was 18.49 km/h pre-HIIT and 18.67 km/h post-HIIT, with a mean training MAS of 20.35 ± 2.01 km/h. Furthermore, no increase in injury risk was observed from training at 110% MAS—contrary to concerns reported by Buchheit and Laursen [28] and Thompson [5].

Wiewelhove et al. [14] found similar neutral-to-positive effects in a 4-week HIIT mesocycle for well-trained intermittent sport athletes, with improvements of 4% in $v\text{VO}_{2\text{max}}$. In the present study, the corresponding MAS increased by 0.97%, and $\text{VO}_{2\text{max}}$ by 0.92%, further supporting the idea that HIIT did not negatively impact performance.

Baek et al. [29] proposed normative HRV values across age groups in healthy individuals. Comparing their reference data to the present study, our runners showed markedly elevated baseline HRV: SDNN was 52.45% and RMSSD 112.09% higher pre-HIIT; post-HIIT, these remained 25.81% and 79.83% higher, respectively. These findings

suggest that long-term aerobic training (mean 10.23 ± 6.11 years) may have contributed to elevated HRV, which was preserved throughout the protocol.

Abad et al. [30] assessed elite Brazilian athletes, including endurance runners, and found lower pre-HIIT HRV values than those observed in our cohort. Their RMSSD and SD1 values were 21% and 22% lower, respectively, compared to ours pre-HIIT, and 2.66% and 3.44% lower post-HIIT. These results support the elevated autonomic cardiac control of our participants, maintained throughout the intervention.

Exercise stimulates the autonomic nervous system (ANS), with sympathetic predominance and parasympathetic withdrawal during exertion and parasympathetic dominance at rest. Consequently, HRV decreases during effort and increases with recovery [7]. Enhanced HRV is associated with greater parasympathetic tone and physical fitness [31,32], while reduced HRV may indicate fatigue or overreaching [33,8].

The current findings confirm this physiological pattern: HRV decreased during the higher-load phases (weeks 1 and 2: 110% MAS, with mean of 34.96 and 22.46 maximal efforts, respectively; taper week: 10.5 efforts) and increased during the recovery phase post-HIIT (Table 1). Thus, the HRV oscillations appear to reflect training-induced fatigue and recovery dynamics.

Although significant statistical changes were detected only in SDNN, RMSSD, and SD2, other HRV indices followed a similar trend, with reductions during peak training and recovery post-intervention (Table 1). Similar results were reported by Nakamura [34], where excessive pre-season loads reduced RMSSD, while moderate loads led to increases, reflecting improved parasympathetic reactivation. Comparable findings are reported by Kaikkonen et al. [35] and Al Haddad et al. [36].

Studies by Flatt and colleagues [37,38] likewise reported non-significant changes in HRV over time, but weekly RMSSD fluctuations indicated preserved autonomic homeostasis despite increased training demands. These findings support the relevance of continuous HRV monitoring during training, as emphasized by Flatt and Esco [39], Flatt [40], and Nakamura [34].

The present study further supports the utility of PNS and SNS indices from the Kubios HRV software as global markers of HRV. These indices are derived from time-domain measures (PNS: Mean RR, RMSSD, SD1; SNS: Mean HR, stress index, SD2), and their deviation from normative values (-2 to $+2$ at rest) offers insight into autonomic regulation [27].

In our sample, PNS decreased by 62% during 110% MAS and 53% during the taper week, recovering to 94.1% of baseline post-HIIT. The SNS index rose from 0.0036 pre-HIIT to 0.2418 (110% MAS) and 0.1845 (taper), then

decreased to -0.4209 post-HIIT. Despite fluctuations, both indices remained near zero, indicating autonomic stability—similar to findings by Lundell et al. [41] in a diving training context.

Additionally, resting mean HR decreased by 4% post-HIIT (from 60.27 to 57.91 bpm), and the stress index declined by 9%. Other HRV indices followed the expected trajectory: reductions during intensive training and increases post-HIIT, returning to near-baseline levels (Table 1).

Parasympathetic reactivation after exercise varies individually and indicates cardiovascular recovery. Well-trained athletes with higher aerobic capacity tend to recover autonomic balance more quickly, with lower resting heart rates and greater HRV. The HIIT protocol applied in this study led to positive adaptations, maintaining both autonomic regulation and cardiorespiratory fitness, without signs of increased physiological stress or fatigue.

V. CONCLUSIONS

HRV proved to be sensitive to the effects of HIIT in the runners investigated, indicating its potential as a valuable tool for monitoring this training model. It is also concluded that HIIT is effective in maintaining athletic performance and safe from the perspective of cardiac autonomic regulation, as evidenced by the absence of chronic maladaptations in sympathetic and parasympathetic indices, as well as in related variables.

CONFLICT of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

METHODOLOGICAL Considerations

The strength of this study is that resting HRV analysis has proven to be an important tool for monitoring HIIT in runners. However, there are limitations that we must address regarding this study. First, we recognize that resting HRV recordings should be recorded at multiple time points: before the first intervention and after the last week of the protocol, during testing, and throughout all training weeks (both sessions). This will allow for appropriate and accurate monitoring of HRV fluctuations across the entire training protocol. Second, a larger sample size could more accurately highlight and reflect the statistical differences in the data analyzed. Further research should be conducted to ensure the accuracy of the findings in this study, so that professionals in the field can acquire the necessary information to appropriately prescribe this type of training.

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